

**PROFESSIONAL CULTURAL COMPETENCE AND TEACHER'S
PROFESSIONALISM: MEANING, CHARACTERISTICS AND INTERRELATIONS**

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10005154>

Globalization is the process of creating a new global political, economic, cultural and informational unity. Competence is a set of interrelated areas (knowledge, skills, skills, business, behavior) of an individual. Competence is the ability to use the acquired knowledge and skills in practice, to solve some practical and theoretical problems in real life.

Professional competence is a set of professional knowledge or an individual professional characteristic that determines the readiness and ability to perform pedagogical activities. Integration describes a new stage of development of the system of international relations in the economic, social and social spheres. Interdisciplinary integration is the unity of knowledge and practical activities at all stages of future teacher training. Globalization of education is aimed at the distance of education, that is, the general availability of education, the availability of many opportunities to master it.

Global thinking is an individual's unique perception of the world around him, feeling that the processes occurring in the world are interconnected and mutually influencing each other, having the ability to successfully live in a multinational, multicultural world, and striving for self-improvement.

An individual is an individual as a subject of social relations and conscious activity. Information is something that has passed through the three filters of the mechanism of receiving information: received - understood - evaluated. Informatization is the use of information technologies and new telecommunication tools that appear due to the development of science during the process of teaching pedagogy, supplementing the content of pedagogical education with new information. A method (Greek methodos - the way to reach the truth) means the way of an ordered action to achieve a goal in a certain way.

Modeling is a theoretical understanding of the pedagogical process. The model depicts the conditions of the pedagogical process, the connection, the system of elements. Pedagogical system is a pedagogical process consisting of many structures and components united with each other for the purpose of education and development of an individual. World culture cannot replace traditional values, they can only be the basis of dialogue between cultures while preserving their diversity. Culture is a collection of people's life experience, education and upbringing, image of the way of life accumulated in their native soil.

Modernization processes in the field of education are carried out first of all from the point of view of the 21st century personality and the place and role of teachers who educate them in national and transnational educational spaces, readiness for international interaction in the context of globalization. After all, in the new situation, the teacher has the task of raising an educated, intelligent citizen of his country and a citizen of the world on the basis of universal democratic and humanistic values.

Such a person is intelligent, has a broad worldview, has a high ability to think in new ways, is eager to learn, has developed patriotism, is capable of competitiveness, and should be formed as a dynamic force and potential that promotes the country's economy and culture. In our

language, globalization, which is used in the form of globalization, globalization, globalization, means any process, course of action, or cultural and social phenomenon, phenomenon, not limited to a single nation, people, culture, civilization, or continent, but the whole planet, terrestrial, a concept that manifests itself at the global level and shows its importance. Globalization is a process, an ongoing, unfinished business.

Globalization means spreading and spreading all over the world, as well as following the impulse of the countries of the world to create a unified human culture. It is known that the Uzbek society cannot be isolated from the influence of the globalization process, which is currently going on intensively, even if it does not want to. Only when every nation, every ethnic group, every state adapts globalization to its own nature, it will benefit from this seemingly dangerous phenomenon.

Only when each nation, each ethnic group, each state adapts globalization to its own nature, it will benefit from this seemingly threatening phenomenon. The process of professional training of teachers according to the Bologna system introduced by our country is also a reflection of the spread of this problem in our country. At the same time, revision of educational content and modernization of technologies at all levels of education is the only way to focus on quality and achieve results.

In this regard, the formation of competencies related to global and cultural education in the future specialist, which is the result of higher education, is an urgent issue. The regulatory and legal basis for effectively solving this problem facing the education sector is reflected in the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan on Education, documents related to education of the Cabinet of Ministers. The professional competence of the teacher is a factor of raising the quality of education:

The professional competence of the teacher is measured by his comprehensive knowledge, teaching skills, mastery of new teaching methods. The more educated and creative the teacher is, the wider his scope of competence will be. The concept of "competence" is introduced in the field of pedagogy as a result of paying special attention to the subjective experience of a person. Competence means being well-informed, expert in a certain field, capable of making an authoritative decision on some issues. The main conditions of the teacher's professional competence:

1. Interpersonal and work communication.
2. Learning the economic, social, legal, moral, psychological aspects of the service.
3. Readiness to adapt the service to a new situation, to make management decisions.
4. Training potential in performing practical professional tasks
5. Proficiency in the use of certain methods depending on specific situations.
6. Ability to make effective decisions.

“Competence is not only professional knowledge, but the ability to develop a person's general culture and creative potential”, sums up the well-known scholar T. G. Brahe. Therefore, today's teacher should not only supplement his professional knowledge, but also constantly work creatively. Aren't the words of Uly Abay: “For free, human beings surpass human beings in terms of intelligence, science, dignity, and character” - words that reveal the essence of the teaching profession? Therefore, if we say what is required of a teacher, who is a technologist of his work, having a strong professional skill, then the content of the teacher's creative activity consists of research activity and personal research. The transition to a new system of result-

oriented education requires the formation of a new approach to the professional qualification of teachers, as well as the constant development of their competences. Only a highly cultured person seeks and finds ways to solve these needs. A quick-thinking, deep-witted, competitive, change-oriented, highly creative, mature professional, searching, researching, creative and innovative teacher is the order of today's society. To become a qualified teacher only when each lesson is turned into a source of independent learning, research and fruitful work. problem is solved. “Teaching is not just an ordinary skill, it is an art that finds something new”, says Zhusipbek Aimautov.

Teacher profession is one of the most important professions in the modern world. The future of human civilization depends on his efforts. A professional teacher is a single person who spends most of his time educating and teaching children. If the process of teaching children with a teacher stops, then a crisis will inevitably follow. To work successfully, a teacher needs not only subject and psychological-pedagogical knowledge, but also a special skill - the ability to communicate. A person begins to master communication skills from an early age.

The profession of a teacher belongs to the type of “person-to-person” profession (according to the typology of psychologist E.A. Klimov). Therefore, the ability to communicate is a leading, professionally important quality for a teacher. Communication is the basis of pedagogical activities. How the teacher communicates with the students depends on the level of their cognitive interest in the subject, and therefore on their motivation to study.

Pedagogical communication style determines the efficiency of students' acquisition of subject knowledge and skills, affects the culture of interpersonal communication, creates the appropriate moral and psychological climate of the learning process. Communication is an important condition for the socialization of an individual.

The teacher's communicative culture is one of the important components of the professional-pedagogical culture. The need for its formation is due to the fact that the teacher is constantly involved in the process of communication, which ensures a diverse and comprehensive relationship with people who will be communication partners within the educational process. These relations appear and develop in the process of joint activity, an important condition for its implementation is communication.

Communication is the basis of pedagogical activities. It depends on the teacher's communication with students, the level of their cognitive interest in the subject, and determines the effectiveness of students' acquisition of subject knowledge and skills. Influences the culture of interpersonal communication, creates an appropriate moral and psychological climate of the learning process. Communication is an important condition for the socialization of an individual. According to a number of psychologists, it is possible to talk about the teacher's communicative culture:

- creative thinking;
- the culture of speech activity, which is understood as the mastery of normative speech that avoids lexical, stylistic, orthographic and other violations;
- culture of self-adjustment to the relationship and psycho-emotional regulation of its situation;
- movement culture and movement plasticity;
- culture of acceptance of communicative actions;
- the culture of emotions.

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